

ROLE OF FRUIT THINNING ON APPLE FRUIT QUALITY

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Abstract: Quality fruit production possesses many cultivation activities to get marketable fruit worldwide as well in Uzbekistan. In this review study, we discussed ways for quality apple production with fruit thinning. Fruit thinning activities already had been examined by scientists with thinning methods and on several apple cultivars. Therefore, this study addressed pieces of evidence that will be effective for apple growers which; there are problems with apple fruit size and tradable attributes.

Key words: Chemical thinning, Fruit size, Hand thinning, Mechanical thinning.

Introduction: For producing quality apple fruits, growers should be actively managed all processes of orchard activities gradually during the entire length of tree growth. Tree growth considering hold those periods from flowering to harvesting. The quality produced apples mark the main point of income with selling best price. On the other hand, fruit thinning in apple growers may obtain yearly fruit production and avoid fruit bear biennially. Therefore, this research has been reviewed that related to apple fruit quality by fruit thinning.

History of fruit thinning: Flower and fruit thinning were explained precisely by researchers (Ferry and Warrington, 2003). Around 2000 years before, Theophrastus informed that growers mentioned the tendency of fruit trees to overcrop and described removing some crops (Thompson, 1957). Bedford and Pickering (1916) fruit alternate reported that alternate bearing could be managed by hand-thinning at the bloom stage instead of fruit thinning 6-8 weeks after full bloom. There are three methods known for fruit thinning those are hand-thinning, mechanical thinning and chemical thinning.

Hand thinning: Hand thinning is a reliable method for fruit size and to regulate biennial bearing. Habitually, hand thinning starts when tree bloom and then repeated the fruit's size become 18 mm after a certain period. Specially applied time of flower and fruit thinning will be effective for next year reflowering (Tromp, 2000).

Mechanical thinning: The second method of fruit thinning is mechanical thinning but are generally practiced only for stone fruits. Familiar ways of mechanical thinning are group and rope thinning. Group thinning was applied by shaking the limb, and this method do not applied to apples because of when used apple fruit become bruise. However, some group thinning experiments were used for 'Delicious' apple cultivars with intervals from 4 to 12 weeks after full bloom. As a result, tree shakes affect only fruit size but did not affect the number of fruits per tree.

On the other hand, peaches were thinned with rope thinners. Apples do not be thinned by rope thinners because they will damage apple spurs. While rope thinners were applied, sometimes do not be helpful. Therefore, they will be repeated more than one time (Dennis, 2000).

Chemical thinning: Chemical thinning is a widely practiced method and more efficient than other techniques. Two characters of chemical thinning are determined, and these are caustic compounds and hormone use. Caustic thinning some compounds were used the time to time first used one known as tar distillates with partially remove flowers. Sodium dinitro-ortho cresylate was served broadly and efficiently until 1990 in arid regions when registration was revoked. The synthetic auxins naphthyl acetic acid (NAA) and its amide (NAAm) are the most extensively utilized thinners for apples and pears and reduce preharvest drop as hormone use. Moreover, abscisic acid (ABA), 6-benzyl adenine (6-BA) and gibberellins (GA) are also used as chemical thinners. Furthermore, the chemicals mentioned above thinners are more efficient in arid areas and do not affect humidity (Greene and Costa, 2013).

Chemical thinning is helpful for apples with its availability and affectability. And economically profitable than hand and mechanical thinning. Especially in Uzbekistan reason for Uzbekistan apple orchards arider and not so much observed humidity in the growing season of apples.

Fruit thinning is a vital part of apple production and tree management, especially with improved fruit size, fruit quality, and minimizing as long as possible alternate bearing in apples.

Conclusion: In summary, to produce quality, marketable and exportable apple fruit thinning

practice is crucial for apple growers, and an essential point of fruit thinning solve the problem of fruiting every two years. Hence, growers hold time applying chemical thinning and have to find different computable types of chemicals according to their regions and available products from their markets.

References:

1. Costa G., Blanke M. M., Widmer A. (2013). Principles of thinning in fruit tree crops - Needs and novelties. *Acta Horticulturae*, 998, 17–26.
2. D. C. Ferre, I. J. W. (2003). *Apples Botany, Production and Uses* (I. J. W. D. C. Ferre, ed.). CABI Publishing.
3. Dennis F. G. (2000). The history of fruit thinning. *Plant Growth Regulation*, 31(1–2), 1–16.
4. Link H. (2000). Significance of flower and fruit thinning on fruit quality. *Plant Growth Regulation*, 31(1–2), 17–26.
5. Pickering S. (1916). The fruiting of trees in consecutive seasons. *The Journal of Agricultural Science*, 8(1), 131–135.
6. Tromp J. (2000). Flower-bud formation in pome fruits as affected by fruit thinning. *Plant Growth Regulation*, 31(1–2), 27–34.